

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 2 September, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

Editor-in-Chief

Solomon Olubunmi, PhD

Editor

Samson Olowo Kolawole, PhD

Associate Editors

Vincent Okwudili Iweama, PhD
Nwachi Loveday Agwu, PhD
Ayogu Chiagolum Elochukwu
Shamsudeen Alhassan Musa
Sagir Lawal, PhD
Vahyala Adamu Tari, PhD
Ubong Evans Abraham, PhD
Kabiru Umar, PhD
Valentine Ayo Mebu, PhD
Ajene Sunday Apeh, PhD

Editorial Advisory Board

Prof. Benjamin Oladapo Olley,
Prof. Benjamin Oluwabunmi Omolayo
Prof. Mike Duru,
Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse,
Prof. Hussaini Tukur Hassan,
Prof. Junaidu Muhammad Kurawa
Prof. Canice Esidene Erunke,
Prof. Ahmad Audu Maiyaki,
Prof. Zubairu Kwambo Dagona,
Prof. Abu Maji,
Dr Bello Halilu Rogo,
Dr Abdulrazaq Ibrahim

Effects of Brand Image Strategies on Customers Loyalty to Soft Drink Products: A Study of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' Products in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Ikechukwu Bernard Eze

Department of Management Science,
Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria.

E-mail: bernardeze9@gmail.com; +2347037674493

Abstract

Recently, information from social media has it that consumers of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products in Enugu State are displaying fluctuating and unstable loyalty to the products of the companies. Although the authenticity of the information is not verified, another rumour has it that the fluctuating and unstable loyalty may not be too far from the frequent and unorganized use of brand image strategies by the companies to attract more customers which some consumers now rightly or wrongly interpret as a source of confusion and therefore preventing them from making intelligent decisions on which brand of the products to buy. It is against the backdrop that this study examined the effects of brand image strategies on customers loyalty to soft drink products with Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products in Enugu State as a case study. The research specifically investigated how the brand image strategies of the firms under study affect customers' trust and repeat purchase, and the multiplying effects of their effects on customers' loyalty to the firms. Survey design was adopted for the study. The researcher worked with a conservative customer population estimate of 180 respondents, which also formed the sample size for the research and was shared equally among the three senatorial zones of the state, with each zone having 60 respondents. Individual respondents from each zone were selected through a convenience sampling technique. The questionnaire formed the data collection instrument for the research, while the data collected were analyzed with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) under a 95% confidence level with a 0.05% margin of error with the aid of SPSS version 22. At the end of the analysis and interpretation of results, the research revealed that brand image strategies affect customers' trust and repeat purchase and that the multiplying effects of their purchasing decisions affect customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products in Enugu State. Based on the findings, the research therefore concluded that brand image strategies positively and significantly affect customers loyalty and therefore their purchasing behaviour for Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products in Enugu State and by extension, Nigeria in general. Standing on the conclusion, the management of the firms – Coca Cola and 7up Bottling Companies were advised to give adequate business attention to brand image strategies planning and implementation as a short-term measure to attract and convince customers to patronize their products but were equally encouraged to engage in product quality development as a long-term measure not only to convince customers to patronize their products but to retain them for future transactions.

Keywords: Brand image strategies, trust, repeat purchase, customer loyalty.

Article history:

Received: 19 November 2024

Reviewed: 20 February 2025

Accepted: 29 March 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Eze, I. B. (2025).

Effects of Brand Image Strategies on Customers Loyalty to Soft Drink Products: A Study of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' Products in Enugu State, Nigeria**Introduction**

Customer loyalty describes an ongoing emotional relationship between a firm and its customers, manifesting itself in how willing the customers are to engage with the firm in terms of repeat purchase of its products instead of competitors' products. Loyalty is the by-product of customers' positive experience and trust with a company and its products. Thakur (2021) stated that loyalty is a customer's intent or predisposition to buy from the same seller or buy the same brand again and again, which, according to Thakur, is a result of the assumption that the value received from the said seller or brand is greater than the value obtainable from other competitors or competitive brands. Thakur explained that customer loyalty has two dimensions, consisting of behavioural and attitudinal loyalty. The behavioural loyalty refers to customers' behaviour to repurchase since they enjoy a particular brand or service. Attitudinal loyalty, on the other hand, refers to the emotional and psychological longing of a customer not only to repurchase a given product or service but to recommend it to other people to patronize the same. This explanation of Thakur (2021) is in agreement with the position of Chen and Ching (2019), who posited that customer loyalty consists of two dimensions – attitudinal and behavioural, describing behavioural angles as characterized by consequential actions resulting from loyalty and attitudinal patterns as formative behaviour that results in commitment.

In a competitive market environment, there are many factors that affect customers' loyalty to a company, product, or service and brand image strategies are one of them. Basically, brand image strategies are unique sets of

associations in the minds of customers regarding what a brand stands for and the implied promises the brand makes to buyers. According to Betch and Betch (2022), brand image strategies are the impression of a brand in the minds of customers of a brand's total personality which may be imaginary or real, but capable of influencing the perception of customers with regard to the quality and performance of a product or service. Explaining further, Betch and Betch stated that they are usually developed through advertising campaigns with a consistent theme over time and validated through the direct satisfaction experiences of the customers. Hess and Strong (2022), in their contribution, asserted that reputable brand image strategies enable customers to distinguish their needs that the brand fulfils and differentiate the company from other competitors and enhance customers repeat purchase for the brand.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of this study emanates from the recently noticed fluctuating and unstable loyalty that manifests from the purchase behaviour of customers of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State. Unconfirmed rumour making around has it that the fluctuating and unstable customers loyalty is as a result of frequent and unorganized use of brand image strategies by the companies to attract and convince customers to patronise one company's products instead of other competitors. The use of this brand image strategy as a competitive marketing weapon by these firms today is so pronounced that some consumers, rightly or wrongly, feel that the strategies are confusing them from making wise decisions on which brand of the products to patronize instead of the strategies positively helping them to

engage in intelligent buying decisions that will increase their trust and loyalty to the firms. It is the zeal to ascertain the actual effects of brand image strategies on customers loyalty with reference to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products that prompted the researcher to embark on this research with Enugu State as the study area.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is the researcher's understanding of how the variables in his study connect with each other. According to Miles and Huberman (1994), a conceptual framework is a visual or written statement, one that explains either graphically or in narrative form the key variables to be studied in research and the presumed relationships among them. With regards to the current study, the conceptual framework demonstrates the effects of brand image strategies on trust and repeat purchase and their multiplying effects on customers loyalty. A diagrammatic display of the conceptual framework for the current study is shown below.

Figure 1.1: A conceptual framework showing the effects of brand image strategies on trust and repeat purchase, with their multiplying effects on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products in Enugu State.

Source: Adapted from Miles & Huberman (1994).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the effects of brand image strategies on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies

products in Enugu State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Find the effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
2. Assess the effects of brand image strategies on customers' repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
3. Examine the effects of trust on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
4. Evaluate the effects of repeat purchase on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Statement of Hypotheses

- HO₁: There are no significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
- HO₂: There are no significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
- HO₃: There are no significant effects of trust on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.
- HO₄: There are no significant effects of repeat purchase on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu state.

Review of Related Literature

The focus here was on the extant literature that is related in one way or the other to the current study.

Brand Image Strategies

In the opinion of Keller (2023), brand image strategies are the set of beliefs, ideas, and impressions that customers hold regarding a product or service. Koo (2022), in his contribution, opined that in a competitive

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

market environment, brand image strategies are useful as they enhance customers loyalty, brand equity, brand performance, and purchasing habits of customers. In the words of Faicloth et al (2021), brand image strategies have been conceptualized and operationalized or measured in many ways. Explaining further, Faicloth et al pointed out that they have been assessed or measured based on brand values/benefits and attributes or by using the brand image scale proposed by Malhotra (1981). Corroborating the view of Faicloth et al (2001), Hsich et al (2021) stated that the measurement of brand image strategies based on Malhotra's (1981) proposal could assist organizations or marketers in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of a particular brand and the perceptions of customers towards their services or products as well. Speaking further, Hsich et al emphasized that a successful brand image strategies enable customers to identify the needs that the brand satisfies and equally differentiate the brand from its competitors and consequently raise the likelihood that customers will patronize the brand. In their contribution, Kandampully and Suhartano (2020) asserted that a service or product that continuously holds a favourable image in the eyes of the customers would absolutely obtain a competitive position in the marketplace, increase market share as well and enhance organizational performance in terms of profit. Buttressing their points, Kandampully and Suhartano pointed out that many empirical studies have proven that favourable brand image strategies lead to customer loyalty, positive purchase behaviour, brand equity, and brand performance. Dick and Basu (2020) in their study asserted that the success of a brand image strategy could generate customers awareness regarding the dignity of the brand and so optimize the profitability of the company due to customers' purchase of the product or service from the company.

Speaking on the benefits of brand image strategies to organizations, Nandan (2021) emphasized that the benefits of brand image strategies can be divided into experiential, functional, and symbolic. The experiential benefits, according to Nandan, indicate what it felt like to use the service or product, and these generally are associated with product-related attributes. The functional benefits, he said, are associated with the intrinsic values of service or product consumption, and these generally are associated with the attributes related to the product or service. Similarly, Nandan explained that the symbolic benefits were related to the underlying needs for individual expression or social approval and outer-directed self-esteem, which are generally associated with attributes which are not related to the product or service.

Customer Loyalty

Contributing in the area of loyalty, Jones and Sasser (2019) identified three parts of customer loyalty, which they said consist of re-buy intention, primary level behaviour, and secondary level behaviour. According to Jones and Sasser, re-buy intention refers to future intention of a consumer to repurchase a product or service, while primary level behaviour denotes the practical and immediate re-visiting behaviour of a consumer to a product or service. Secondary level behaviour, on the other hand, refers to the willingness of a customer to recommend a product or service to others, which enhances customer loyalty through human relationships. In the opinion of Dick and Basu (2020), customer loyalty describes the relationship between a customer's relative attitude and repeat patronage. Their thinking was in line with that of Jones and Sasser (2019), but with small modifications and expansion. Standing on the premise of their definition, Dick and Basu proposed four types of customer loyalty based on relative attitude and patronage behaviour, and aptly

demonstrated it with a matrix as shown below in Figure 2.1

Relative Attitude	High	Loyalty	Latent
	Low	Spurious	No loyalty
		High	Low
		Repeat Patronage	

Figure 2.1: Dick and Basu loyalty

(a) No Loyalty. No loyalty refers to customers with a low relative attitude and low repeat patronage toward a product or service. This can occur when competing brands in the market are seen as similar.

(b) Spurious Loyalty. This is a situation where customers have a low attitude and high repeat patronage for a product or service. Spurious loyalty occurs where the consumer undertakes repeat buying due to situational variables such as access, convenience or shelf placement. It can equally happen or manifest where there are no genuine alternatives or the consumer is technically or socially forced to buy a given product or service because of some quasi-contractual arrangement or membership status, which creates difficulties for switching.

(c) Latent Loyalty. Latent loyalty is characterized by a high relative attitude and low repeat patronage by consumers for a given product or service. This type of loyalty manifests itself when situational factors override a strong, favourable attitude. A typical example is where a person may have a preferred restaurant but may not patronize it because of a friend’s recommendation for another restaurant.

(d) Loyalty. This is a situation where consumers have a high relative attitude and high repeat patronage for a given product or service. For marketers, true loyalty is the ideal situation and what every firm strives to achieve for its products and services.

In business, creating truly loyal customers is not an easy task. It occurs as a result of multiple positive interactions between a firm and its customers that build up a feeling of trust over time. There are many ways through which companies can attract customers to their products and provide satisfaction to them with the hope of not only retaining them for future transactions but to making them loyal customers. A loyalty marketing programme is one of them. Loyalty marketing is an approach to marketing based on strategic management in which a firm focuses on growing and retaining existing customers through incentives. Gallo (2021), in his contribution in the area of customer loyalty, stated that a loyalty marketing programme is built on the insight or premise that it costs 15 -20 times more to get a new customer than it is to retain the one already acquired. Organizations use a variety of loyalty programmes to strengthen customers’ attitudes towards their products or services in order to retain them, minimize customer defections, and strengthen loyalty bonds with existing customers. Specifically, there are two types of loyalty programmes – reward and recognition.

In a reward programme, the customer accumulates points for each purchase and the points can subsequently be exchanged for products while recognition programme operates on a quasi-membership basis where the customer is issued with a card that upon presentation leads to various entitlements such as free upgrades, special privileges or access to products or services that are not normally available to non-members and that acknowledges the loyal customer’s “VIP” status. While reward programmes are activated by the customers’ zeal for material possessions, recognition programmes are energized by the customers’ need for esteem, recognition, and status. Many businesses’ loyalty programmes are hybrid in nature,

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

combining elements of both reward and recognition.

Customer Trust. In our social world, trust is key in interpersonal and business interactions. Tabrani et al. (2018) defined customer trust as the willingness of a customer to rely on an exchange partner in whom he or she has confidence. Explaining further, Tabrani et al. emphasized that trust also relates to the perceived credibility and benevolence of the company rendering the service. Credibility, according to Tabrani et al., indicates a customer's perception that the words and promises of a service company can be trusted, while benevolence indicates a customer's belief that a service company's motives and intents are beneficial to its customers. Gefen (2000), in his opinion, explained that customer trust is the belief of a customer that the seller will perform in a commercially responsible way and thus will meet the customer's expectations, devoid of taking any undue advantage of him or her. Buttressing his point, Gefen posited that trust enables customers to share personal information with a seller based on the belief that the information will stay confidential. Gefen stated that it is trust that makes buyers pay for products and services before using them, and to act on the advice of the seller. Gefen therefore pointed out that when a seller is regarded as trustworthy by customers, there is a high probability that they will share important commercial and even social information as a sign of the strength of the relationship.

Customer Repeat Purchase. A repeat purchase is the purchase by a consumer of the same brand as bought on a previous occasion. A repeat purchase is an indicator of the degree of customer loyalty to a brand, which is a function of the satisfaction the customer derives from the consumption or usage of the product. It is also an opportunity for marketers

to establish long-term customer relationships with the expectation of customers' higher usage of the product in the future. A high number of repeat purchases indicates satisfied and well-retained customers, which reduces new-customer acquisition costs and increases overall profitability. Repeat purchase is important to a seller or marketer because getting a profitable customer to buy from a business for the first time is often difficult and expensive. Jin and Huang (2023), in their contribution, explained that a smart marketer can turn new customers to repeat customers by offering quality products, providing great services, and offering price incentives once in a while to attract and retain them. They therefore stressed that satisfaction and trust are two ingredients that propel customers to repeat purchase for a product or service.

Empirical Review

In research literature, there are numerous extant studies that demonstrated in one way or the other the effects of brand image strategies on customers' purchase behaviour in terms of trust, repeat purchase, loyalty, and other areas. The first is the work of Ramesh (2022) on the topic: Effects of brand image strategies on customer satisfaction and loyalty intention in a retail supermarket chain in the United Kingdom. The research specifically examined the effects of brand image strategies on customer satisfaction and loyalty intention. Also, the relationship between brand image strategies and customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction and loyalty intention. The population, as well as the sample size for the study, was 120 respondents, and they were individually selected through a convenience sampling technique. The data collection instrument was a questionnaire, and the data collected were analyzed with percentages and Regression Analysis with the help of SPSS version 20. The result of the analysis showed that (a) brand image strategies have significant effects on customer satisfaction,

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

(b) brand image strategies have significant effects on customer loyalty intention (c) customer satisfaction has significant effects on loyalty intention. Based on the findings, the research concluded that there are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on customer satisfaction, brand image strategies on loyalty intention, and customer satisfaction on loyalty intention.

Basavaraj and Shivashankar (2023) did research on: The impact of brand image strategies on customer loyalty towards private label brand: The mediating effect of satisfaction. The study area was the Conglomerate City of Karnataka in India. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The researcher worked with a population of 200 customers, which also formed the sample size for the study. Individual respondents were selected through a convenience sampling method. Questionnaire was the data collection instrument. The data collected were analyzed with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the aid of SPSS version 20. The result showed that there are positive relationships between brand image strategies and customer loyalty, between brand image strategies and satisfaction, between satisfaction and customer loyalty, and that satisfaction mediates the relationship between brand image strategies and customer loyalty.

Anupama (2021) carried out research in Indonesia on the topic: The impact of brand image strategies on customer loyalty and commitment. The specific objective of the research was to investigate how Laptop brand image affects customers' buying behaviour in terms of loyalty and commitment. The survey formed the research design for the study. The population for the study was 98 respondents. The sample size was also 98 respondents, with individual respondents selected through a convenience sampling technique.

Questionnaire was the data collection instrument used for the research. The data collected were analyzed with Factor Analysis and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The result revealed that buyers' decisions for Laptops were influenced by brand image strategies or association. The research therefore concluded that there is a positive relationship between brand image strategies and customer loyalty and commitment to Laptop with regard to buying decisions.

Gap in Literature

Looking at the extant research reviewed above on how product or service brand image strategies influence or affect consumers' buying behaviour, it is obvious that there are geographical and industry gaps between the extant research and the current study. None of the research was done in Nigeria – geographical gap and the industries in which the researchers focused attention on different from the one the current research focused on – industry gap. All these are knowledge gaps which formed the limitations on the part of the extant researches which the current study filled in the area of brand image strategies and consumer buying behaviour literature in the area of soft drink products as the present work now enrich the literature with current information on the effects of brand image strategies on consumers buying behaviour with not only emphasis on soft drink products but with Nigerian background.

Methodology

The study was survey research anchored on methodological triangulation. The researcher worked with a conservative population estimate of 180 customers/respondents, which also served as the sample size for the research. The 180 respondents were shared equally through a judgmental sampling technique across the three senatorial zones of the state – Enugu North, Enugu East, and Enugu West, with each zone having 60 respondents, and

data collection focused on one local government per zone. Nsukka local government in Enugu North, Enugu North

local government in Enugu East, and Udi local government in Enugu West. Individual respondents were selected through a convenience sampling technique. Questionnaire formed the data collection instrument for the research. The questions were designed based on a modified Likert 4-point scale, such as Strongly agree-4, Agree-3, Disagree-2, Strongly disagree-1. The data collected were analyzed with a statistical tool – Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the aid of SPSS version 22 under a 95% confidence level with a 0.05% margin of error.

Data Presentation, Analysis, Results, and Discussion of Findings

A total of 180 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the three senatorial zones of the state, and they were properly filled out and returned. Therefore, the decisions on the research were based on these 180 valid copies of the questionnaire.

Biodata Presentation of the Sampled Data

Information from the pie chart above shows that 100 respondents were used for the research, of which 56% were males, while 80, representing 44% were females. From the bar chart, 44% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 18-40 years, while 33% are within 41-60 years. 23% respondents are 61-80 years old.

Bivariate Analysis of Sampled Data, i.e., Hypotheses Testing

Four hypotheses were tested in this research, and they were tested with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) under 95% confidence level with a significance level of 0.05.

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 and accept H_1 if P is less than 0.05.

H_{01} : There are no significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Table 4.1 Result of Bivariate Analysis between Brand Image Strategies and Customers Trust

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	350.000	1	350.000	2.04	.01 ^b
	Residual	.000	2	.000		
	Total	180.000	3			

a. Dependent Variable: Customers' trust

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand image strategies

Decision. Information from Table 4.1 above indicates that there are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	350.000	1	350.000	1.05	.000 ^b
	Residual	.000	2	.000		
	Total	180.000	3			

a. Dependent Variable: Customers loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Trust

customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State. This is true because the ANOVA table P value is 0.01, which is less than the standard P value of 0.05. (F=2.04, df=1, 2 P=0.01). Therefore, H₀ is rejected, and H₁ is accepted. Brand image strategies positively affect customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Ho₂: There are no significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Table 4.2 Result of Bivariate Analysis between Brand Image Strategies and Customers Repeat Purchase

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	350.000	1	350.000	2.06	.003 ^b
	Residual	.000	2	.000		
	Total	180.000	3			

a. Dependent Variable: Customers repeat purchase

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand image strategies

Decision. Results from Table 4.2 show that there are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on customer repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State. The ANOVA table P value is 0.03 is less than the standard P value of 0.05. (F=2.06, df=1, 2 P=0.03). Therefore, H₀ is rejected, and H₁ is accepted. This means that brand image strategies positively affect customers' repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Ho₃: There are no significant effects of trust in customers loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up

Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Table 4.3 Result of Bivariate Analysis between Trust and Customers Loyalty

Decision. Table 4.3 reveals that there are positive and significant effects of trust in customers loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State. The ANOVA table P value is 0.00, which is less than the standard P value of 0.05. (F=1.05, df=1, 2 P=0.00). Therefore, H₀ is rejected, and H₁ is accepted. This means that trust affects customers' loyalty positively to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Ho₄: There are no significant effects of repeat purchase on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu state.

Table 4.4 Result of Bivariate Analysis between Repeat Purchase and Customers Loyalty.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	350.000	1	350.000	3.05	.003 ^b
	Residual	.000	2	.000		
	Total	180.000	3			

a. Dependent Variable: Customers loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Repeat purchase

Decision. Information from table 4.4 above indicates that there are positive and significant effects of repeat purchase on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State. The ANOVA table P value is 0.03, which is less than the standard P value of 0.05. (F=3.05, df=1, 2 P=0.03). Therefore, H₀ is rejected, and H₁ is accepted. This means that customers' repeat purchase affects positively customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State.

Summary of Findings

At the end of analysis and interpretation of results, the research recorded the following findings.

1. There are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust in Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State
2. There are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' repeat purchase of Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State
3. There are positive and significant effects of trust in customers loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State
4. There are positive and significant effects of repeat purchase on customers' loyalty to Coca-Cola and 7up Bottling Companies products in Enugu State

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of findings from the statistical calculations of the hypotheses and interpretation of results showed that the findings were in agreement with the objectives of the study and some extant research findings in the area of influence or effects of brand image strategies on consumers' buying behaviour in terms of trust, repeat purchase, and loyalty.

Specifically, the findings of hypotheses 1,2,3, and 4 that there are positive effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust and repeat purchase, and that the multiplying effects have positive impacts on customers' loyalty to the products of the firms under study, were also in line with the results of some extant research in the area.

For example, the findings aligned with the results of the works of Ramesh (2022), Basavaraj and Shivashankar (2023), and Anupama (2021), to mention but a few. Ramesh (2022) did research on the effects of brand image strategies on customer

satisfaction and loyalty intention and discovered that there was a positive relationship between brand image strategies and customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Basavaraj and Shivashankar (2023) examined the impact of brand image strategies on customer loyalty with satisfaction as the mediating variable and got the result that there was a positive relationship between brand image strategies and customer loyalty and that satisfaction played a significant role as a mediator between brand image strategies and customer loyalty.

Anupama (2021), on his part, conducted a study on the impact of brand image strategies on customer loyalty and commitment, and the result revealed that there was a positive relationship between brand image strategies and customer loyalty and commitment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings recorded from the study, the research therefore concluded that there are positive and significant effects of brand image strategies on customers' trust and repeat purchase of Coca Cola and 7up Bottling Companies' products and that the multiplying effects positively affect customers' loyalty to the firms and their products in Enugu State and by implication Nigeria in general.

Standing on the findings and conclusion, the management of the firms – Coca Cola and 7up Bottling Companies were advised to give adequate business attention to brand image strategies planning and implementation as a short-term measure to attract and convince customers to patronize their products but were equally encouraged to invest in quality research and development as a long-term measure not only to attract customers but to retain them for future transactions.

References

- Anupama, S.D. (2021). The impact of brand image on customer commitment and loyalty. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management, and Applied Sciences*, 7(8), 46-63.
- Basavaraj, S., & Shivashankar, K. (2023). The impact of brand image on customer loyalty towards private label brands: The mediating effect of satisfaction. *International Journal of Marketing and Financial Management*, 5(8), 43-50.
- Belch, G.E., & Belch, M. (2020). *Advertising and promotion: An integrated marketing communication perspective*. (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Chen, J., & Ching, R.K.H. (2022). The effects of mobile phones on customer relationship management with reference to customer loyalty. *Journal of International Management Studies*, 4(1), 51-59.
- Dick AS and Basu K (2020). Customer loyalty: Towards an integrated conceptual framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing*, 22(2): 99–113
- Faircloth, J.B., Capella, L.M., & Alford, B.L. (2021). The effect of brand image and brand attitude on brand equity. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 9(3), 61–74.
- Gallo, A. (2023). The value of keeping the right customers. *Harvard Business Review*, 6(2), 31-45.
- Hess, J., & Story, J. (2022). Trust-based commitment: Multidimensional consumer-brand relationships. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 21(5), 321-345.
- Hsich, M.H., Pan, S.L., & Setiono, R. (2021). Product, corporate, and country-image dimensions and buyer behaviour: A multicounty analysis. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 32(3), 251–270.
- Jin, L., & Huang, Y. (2023). When financial reward does not work: The differential impacts of financial versus non-financial rewards in referral reward programmes. *Journal of Marketing*, 8(3), 210- 220.
- Jones, T.O., & Sasser, J.W.E. (2019). Why satisfied customers' defect? *Harvard Business Review*, 73(6), 88–99.
- Kandampully, J., & Suhartanto, D. (2020). Customer loyalty in the hotel industry: The role of customer satisfaction and image. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 12(6), 346-351.
- Keller, K.L. (2023). *Building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Pearson Education Publisher.
- Koo, D.M. (2022). Inter-relationships among store satisfaction, store images and store loyalty among Korean discount retail patrons. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 15(4), 42–71.
- Malhotra, N.K. (1981). A scale to measure person concepts, self-concepts and product concepts. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(4), 456–464.
- Miles, M.B., & Huberman, A.M. (1994). *Quantitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Muhammad, A., & Abdul, S.L. (2023). Impact of brand positioning strategies on consumer standpoint: A consumer's perception. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Behaviour*, 14(1), 109-116.
- Nandan, S. (2021). An exploration of the brand identity-brand image linkage: Communications perspective. *Journal of Brand Management*, 12(4), 264–278.
- Ramesh, N. (2022). The effects of brand image on customer satisfaction and loyalty intention in retail supermarket chain in United Kingdom. *International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 9-26.
- Thakur, R. (2024). Understanding customer relationship management and loyalty: A case of mobile devices for shopping. *Journal of Retailing and Customer Services*, 32(2), 151-163.